

IPBES TCA Chapter 4. Review of literature on the persistent and pervasive relations of domination forged in colonial eras / IPBES transformative change assessment (4.1)

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Description

The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 4 should address a range of constraints and challenges that arise within and between political, legal, technological, physical (e.g., infrastructure), economic/financial and other social systems and the functioning of ecosystems and how these challenges could be overcome. The chapter provides evidence on challenges associated with political, social and economic inequalities, among and within countries. In this context, a review of various dimensions of persistent and pervasive relations of domination, forged in colonial eras, based on expert knowledge and searches was conducted and is further described below.

Process overview

Protocol

The evidence to inform section 4.2.1. was gathered through two searches within three different processes.

Process 1: References based on expert knowledge

To assess the literature on these relations of domination, the author team drew on its research experience on the subject of persistent and pervasive relations of domination, forged in colonial eras, the emerging conceptual framework within which these relations are understood, identifying eight dimensions of this worldview, which were clustered into three more general groups:

- 1) Categorise and Rank
 - a. Categorization
 - b. Stratification
- 2) Measure, Simplify and Manage
 - a. Singularization
 - b. Technocracy
 - c. Quantification
- 3) Justify the taking of resources
 - a. Appropriation
 - b. Extraction
 - c. Concentration

The team then selected 3-5 examples of work for each dimension that empirically demonstrates how those dimensions of the persistent and pervasive relations of domination that shape contemporary understandings of nature and biodiversity become barriers to transformative change in the context of biodiversity to then feed the search in Research Rabbit. To do so, the team first suggested articles from their own expert experience. The team then solicited suggestions from experts in their networks who either have conducted empirical work on biodiversity and conservation, or who are deeply engaged with these literatures. Five experts responded with suggested cases.

The team reviewed the collected references and agreed on core cases for each dimension of these relations of domination.

Number of articles selected for each dimension **(A)**:

- Categorization: 6 articles
 - Stratification: 4 articles
 - Singularization: 3 articles
 - Technocracy: 5 articles
 - Quantification: 4 articles
 - Appropriation: 6 articles
 - Extraction: 5 articles
 - Concentration: 2 articles
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Process 2: Search using multiple new tools

As this is a very new area of inquiry, the current literature on biodiversity loss and its drivers does not lend itself to keyword searches for the relations of domination. This is not a current focus area in the literature, with most cases illustrating the importance of these relations in the course of other investigations. Therefore, a keyword search would have missed relevant cases while returning a huge amount of irrelevant literature. To address this issue, the team conducted two parallel searches using new bibliographic search tools – Research Rabbit and Elicit. The searches were run in parallel to allow for cross-checking of references across the two tools, and to capture the widest possible set of references. By using both tools independently, the team sought to avoid any tool-specific issues with the search.

Details search 1:

For one part of this paired search, the team conducted a search aided by Research Rabbit. Research Rabbit is a free online “citation-based literature mapping tool”. It is a visual literature review software mapping tool, which works from small sets of articles to identify similar publications in the literature. The search was carried out in English.

Based on the examples selected in the first process, the team then anchored in searches for cases in Research Rabbit. The first 100 results returned under each dimension were collected, which resulted in a consolidated list of 498 potential cases (many cases appeared in searches under more than one dimension).

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** citation-based literature mapping search
- **Search language:** English
- **Search engine:** Research Rabbit
- **Search method:** feeding a list of 33 articles **(A)** into Research Rabbit
- **Sample extracted:** 498 potential cases **(B)**
- **Treatment applied:** the Research Rabbit results were analysed and consolidated, removing duplicate mentions. There were substantial duplicate mentions, as the 800 articles found – 100 for each dimension – were consolidated down to 498.

Details search 2:

Elicit (elicit.org) uses sentences instead of keywords to inform its searches. For this part of the search, questions were developed, organised around each cluster of dimensions (rather than the specific dimensions) after seeing the heavy overlap in cases emerging from the Research Rabbit search, for Elicit to identify relevant literature. The first 100 references returned by Elicit under each search sentence were collected (in some cases, more than 150 references). Because there was overlap between the Research Rabbit results and the Elicit results, a consolidated list of references was made by taking the Elicit and Research Rabbit results, lining them up and removing duplicates, leading to the final list.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** question-based literature search
 - **Search language:** English
 - **Search engine:** Elicit.org
 - **Search method:** feeding a list of 30 questions into Elicit
 - **List of questions:**
- 1) Categorize and rank

- a. What are examples of ways coloniality produces specific ways of ranking and categorising nature and biodiversity?
 - i. How does the ranking and categorising of nature and biodiversity under coloniality create barriers to change?
 - b. What are examples of ways coloniality produces categorizations of nature and biodiversity?
 - i. How does the categorization of nature and biodiversity under coloniality create barriers to change?
 - c. What are examples of ways coloniality produces rankings of nature and biodiversity?
 - i. How does the ranking of nature and biodiversity under coloniality create barriers to change?
 - d. What are examples of ways coloniality produces stratifications of nature and biodiversity?
 - i. How does the stratification of nature and biodiversity under coloniality create barriers to change?
- 2) Measure, simplify and manage
- a. What are examples of ways coloniality produces specific ways of measuring, simplifying and managing nature and biodiversity?
 - i. How does the measurement, simplification and management of nature and biodiversity under coloniality create barriers to change?
 - b. What are examples of ways coloniality singularises nature and biodiversity?
 - i. How does the singularization of nature and biodiversity under coloniality create barriers to change?
 - c. How does coloniality simplify nature and biodiversity?
 - i. How does the simplification of nature and biodiversity under coloniality create barriers to change?
 - d. What are examples of ways coloniality singularises nature and biodiversity?
 - i. How does the singularization of nature and biodiversity under coloniality create barriers to change?
 - e. What are examples of ways coloniality produces technocratic approaches to nature and biodiversity?
 - i. How do technocratic approaches to nature and biodiversity under coloniality create barriers to change?
 - f. What are examples of ways coloniality produces quantifications of nature and biodiversity?
 - i. How does the quantification of nature and biodiversity under coloniality create barriers to change?
- 3) Justify the taking of resources
- a. What are examples of ways coloniality produces specific ways of justifying the taking of resources?
 - i. How does the justification of taking of resources under coloniality create barriers to change?
 - b. What are examples of ways coloniality results in the appropriation of resources?
 - i. How does the appropriation of resources under coloniality create barriers to change?
 - c. What are examples of ways coloniality produces or promotes the extraction of resources?
 - i. How does the promotion of resource extraction under coloniality create barriers to change?
 - d. What are examples of ways coloniality produces concentrations of resources and wealth?
 - i. How does the concentration of resources and wealth under coloniality create barriers to change?

- e. What are examples of ways coloniality results in the securitization of resources and nature?
 - i. How does the securitization of resources and nature under coloniality create barriers to change?
- **Sample extracted:** 738 references **(C)**
- **Treatment applied:** Elicit results also had substantial overlaps across the questions asked.

Overall treatment applied: The results from Research Rabbit and Elicit were then consolidated, resulting in a final list of 1227 references **(D)** containing potential empirical cases of one or more dimensions of these relations of domination acting as a barrier to transformative change in the relationship to and management of biodiversity. An initial rapid screening used the following criteria:

- Is the article an empirical case?
- Does the article illustrate how one or more dimensions of the relations of domination serves as a barrier to transformative change in conservation and biodiversity?

Articles that did not meet both criteria were removed from the analysis, reducing the set of references to 395.

The author team then conducted a second, more detailed screening that involved the reading of each source to capture the context and details of the empirical case and barrier to ensure that the source met the screening criteria above. After detailed screening, the set of cases was reduced to 167 **(E)**.

The 167 remaining references **(E)** were divided among the author team, which analyzed each case and, in short narrative form, summarised how the dimension(s) of these relations of domination represented in each reference served as a barrier to transformative change. In the process of this detailed analysis, an additional 97 references were found to not meet the detailed screening criteria (i.e., did not illustrate a clear empirical case of a barrier to transformative change) and were removed from analysis. The final result was a set of 69 relevant cases **(F)**.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	1_IPBES_TCA_4.1_11_2023_(A)	CSV	8 KB	List of references selected for search on Research Rabbit for Section 4.2.1.
B	2_IPBES_TCA_4.1_11_2023_(B)	CSV	105 KB	498 potential cases extracted from Research Rabbit
C	3_IPBES_TCA_4.1_11_2023_(C)	CSV	213 KB	738 papers extracted from Elicit
D	4_IPBES_TCA_4.1_11_2023_(D)	CSV	242 KB	List of compiled references from Elicit and Research Rabbit
E	5_IPBES_TCA_4.1_11_2023_(E)	CSV	177 KB	List of references after second screening
F	6_IPBES_TCA_4.1_11_2023_(F)	CSV	177 KB	Final list of relevant references for section 4.2.1.